

Case Report

Hypertriglyceridemia-Induced Acute Pancreatitis With New-Onset Diabetic Ketoacidosis in a 55-Year-Old Female With an Incidental Multicystic Pancreatic Mass

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Abstract

A 55-year-old woman with no prior history of diabetes who presented with acute abdominal pain and was found to have severe hyperglycemia (glucose 308 mg/dL), metabolic acidosis (pH < 7.20, bicarbonate < 10 mmol/L), and marked ketonuria (4+), consistent with diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA). Abdominal CT scan revealed a multicystic pancreatic head mass with peripancreatic fat stranding, suggestive of acute pancreatitis. Serum lipase was mildly elevated (183 U/L), and triglycerides were markedly elevated at 3,700 mg/dL, confirming hypertriglyceridemia-associated pancreatitis. The patient was managed with aggressive intravenous fluids, continuous insulin infusion, and electrolyte replacement, which corrected the metabolic derangements and facilitated rapid triglyceride reduction. Supportive management of pancreatitis was initiated concurrently. This case highlights a rare but clinically significant overlap of new-onset DKA, hypertriglyceridemia-induced pancreatitis, and an incidental multicystic pancreatic mass. Early recognition and comprehensive metabolic resuscitation were essential in preventing further deterioration and underscore the importance of evaluating lipid disorders in patients presenting with DKA.

Keywords: Pancreatitis, Diabetic Ketoacidosis, Hypertriglyceridemia, Pancreatic mass

Introduction

Acute pancreatitis is an inflammatory condition with multiple etiologies, most commonly gallstones and alcohol use. Hypertriglyceridemia accounts for approximately 1–10% of cases, typically when triglyceride levels exceed 1,000 mg/dL, and is believed to result from the cytotoxic effects of free fatty acids generated during triglyceride hydrolysis [1].

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is a life-threatening metabolic emergency caused by insulin deficiency. Although more common in type 1 diabetes, it may be the initial presentation of type 2 diabetes. DKA and acute pancreatitis share overlapping symptoms, including abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting, complicating diagnosis. Insulin deficiency in DKA promotes lipolysis and worsens hypertriglyceridemia, creating a cycle that may precipitate pancreatitis [2,3].

The simultaneous occurrence of hypertriglyceridemia induced pancreatitis (HTG-AP) and new-onset DKA is uncommon and requires rapid recognition and coordinated management. The incidental discovery of a multicystic pancreatic mass further complicates diagnostic and therapeutic decision-making. We present a case of a 55-year-old woman with no prior diabetes history who presented with acute abdominal pain and was found to have severe hypertriglyceridemia, new-onset DKA, and a multicystic pancreatic head mass.

Case Presentation

A 55-year-old woman with no significant past medical history presented with four days of progressively worsening right upper-quadrant abdominal pain. The pain was sharp, constant, non-radiating, and rated 8/10. She reported chills, nausea, multiple episodes of non-bilious

vomiting, and two to three episodes of foul-smelling loose stools. She had been unable to tolerate oral intake. She denied prior similar episodes, alcohol use, chest pain, palpitations, syncope, or visual changes.

On admission, she was afebrile but in acute distress with right upper-quadrant and epigastric tenderness. Laboratory evaluation revealed severe hypertriglyceridemia (3,700 mg/dL), hyperglycemia (308 mg/dL), metabolic acidosis (pH < 7.20, bicarbonate < 15 mmol/L), and 4+ ketonuria, consistent with DKA. Hemoglobin A1c was 11.6%, indicating previously undiagnosed diabetes. Lipase was modestly elevated at 183 U/L. Urinalysis showed proteinuria, glucosuria, microscopic hematuria, and pyuria; urine culture grew mixed gram-positive organisms, considered colonization.

Abdominal ultrasound suggested possible gallbladder echogenic material, though artifact could not be excluded. Contrast-enhanced CT revealed a multiloculated cystic lesion in the pancreatic head measuring 7.2 × 6.4 × 5.5 cm, containing tiny calcifications and associated with severe atrophy of the pancreatic body and tail. Mild peripancreatic fat stranding was present. These findings were consistent with pancreatitis, but the cystic lesion raised suspicion for an underlying neoplasm. Tumor markers included CA 19-9 of 75 U/mL and CEA of 3.8 ng/mL.

The patient was diagnosed with acute pancreatitis likely precipitated by severe hypertriglyceridemia in the setting of new-onset DKA. She was managed with bowel rest, aggressive intravenous fluids, analgesia, and continuous

insulin infusion for both DKA resolution and triglyceride reduction. Triglycerides decreased to 711 mg/dL during hospitalization. She was transitioned to basal insulin and started on metformin. Fenofibrate and atorvastatin were initiated for long-term lipid management. Gastroenterology recommended outpatient endoscopic ultrasound with possible fine-needle aspiration (EUS-FNA) to further characterize the pancreatic cyst. Oncology and surgical oncology agreed that no immediate intervention was required but emphasized timely outpatient follow-up.

Table 3. Serum chemistry and lipid profile at admission

Parameter	Admission Value	Reference Range
Sodium	133 mmol/L	136–145 mmol/L
Potassium	3.9 mmol/L	3.5–5.3 mmol/L
BUN	7 mg/dL	6–24 mg/dL
Creatinine	0.61 mg/dL	0.50–1.00 mg/dL
CO ₂	13 mmol/L	20–31 mmol/L
AST	12 U/L	10–36 U/L
ALT	36 U/L	6–29 U/L
Lipase	183 U/L	0–160 U/L
Calcium	8.8 mg/dL	8.6–10.4 mg/dL
HbA1c	11.60%	4–5.7%
LDL	82 mg/dL	
HDL	24 mg/dL	50–80 mg/dL
Triglycerides	3,700 mg/dL	
Alkaline phosphatase	177 U/L	40–116 U/L
Anion gap	20 mmol/L	8–12 mmol/L

Table 1. Urinalysis at presentation

Parameter	Admission Value
Protein	3+
Ketones	4+
Glucose	3+

Table 2. Hemogram at admission

Parameter	Admission Value	Reference Range
WBC	11.5 ×10 ³ /μL	4.8–10.8 ×10 ³ /μL
Hemoglobin	16.1 g/dL	12–15.5 g/dL
Hematocrit	41%	34.9–44.5%

Figure 2. Contrast-enhanced CT abdomen

Axial contrast-enhanced computed tomography image demonstrating a multiloculated cystic lesion involving the pancreatic head with associated peripancreatic fat stranding, consistent with acute pancreatitis. Marked atrophy of the pancreatic body and tail is also noted.

The patient's abdominal pain improved, oral intake resumed, and metabolic parameters stabilized. She was discharged home with instructions for close follow-up with gastroenterology, endocrinology, and surgical oncology.

Discussion

This case illustrates a rare triad of hypertriglyceridemia induced acute pancreatitis (HTG-AP), new-onset DKA, and an incidental multicystic pancreatic mass. HTG-AP typically occurs when triglycerides exceed 1,000 mg/dL, leading to pancreatic injury through the release of free fatty acids that cause cytotoxicity, ischemia, and inflammation [1,2]. In this patient, triglycerides reached 3,700 mg/dL, strongly supporting HTG as the precipitating factor.

DKA exacerbates hypertriglyceridemia by promoting lipolysis and reducing lipoprotein lipase activity, creating a vicious cycle that can precipitate pancreatitis [3–6]. Conversely, pancreatitis may worsen hyperglycemia and trigger DKA through systemic inflammation, particularly in individuals with underlying beta-cell dysfunction, as suggested by the elevated HbA1c [7,8].

The incidental 7.2-cm multicystic pancreatic head mass adds diagnostic complexity. Differential diagnoses include intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasm (IPMN), mucinous cystic neoplasm (MCN), serous cystadenoma, pseudocyst, and cystic neuroendocrine tumor [11–13]. The lesion's size, multiloculation, calcifications, and associated pancreatic atrophy raise concern for a premalignant or malignant process. Mildly elevated CA 19-9 further supports the need for EUS-FNA to evaluate for high-risk features [14–18].

Management aligned with established guidelines: aggressive intravenous fluids, continuous insulin infusion, electrolyte repletion, and supportive care for pancreatitis [1,7,19–22]. Triglycerides decreased significantly without plasmapheresis, which is typically reserved for refractory cases or levels >5,000 mg/dL [19–21]. Long-term therapy with fenofibrate, statin therapy, and diabetes management is essential to prevent recurrence [23,24].

This case underscores the importance of evaluating lipid disorders in patients presenting with DKA and abdominal pain, as early recognition can prevent complications such as necrotizing pancreatitis or organ failure [26–28]. It also highlights the need for careful imaging review, as incidental pancreatic cystic lesions may represent clinically significant neoplasms requiring timely evaluation.

Conclusion

This case demonstrates an uncommon but clinically significant presentation of hypertriglyceridemia-induced acute pancreatitis occurring concurrently with new-onset DKA and an incidental multicystic pancreatic mass. The discovery of a large pancreatic cystic lesion underscores the importance of thorough imaging evaluation in pancreatitis and the need for timely outpatient EUS-FNA to assess malignant potential. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for lipid disorders in DKA patients.

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